

Integrated germplasm improvement–upland

Makiling, an improved variety for acid upland areas in the Philippines

T. T. Chang, G. C. Loresto, O. O. Tagumpay, R. P. Parreño, J. Godilano, and M. Obien, IIRRI

The Philippine Seed Board recently approved the release of breeding line IR10147-113-5-1-1-5 as PSBRC-1, popular name Makiling, for planting in acid upland areas. This cultivar was derived from KN-1B-361-1-8-6//E425/IR22///BPI-76*9/Dawn, using parents from Indonesia, West Africa, Philippines, and the U.S.

KN-1B-361-1-8-6 and E425 are sources of drought resistance and tolerance for acid soils. E425 is also resistant to blast and has a deep and thick root system. Recovery ability after

moisture stress is contributed by the BPI-76*9/Dawn parent. Good eating quality is contributed by parents from Indonesia and the Philippines.

Makiling has a green basal leaf sheath. The flag leaf angle is intermediate. Under favorable conditions, panicle length is about 25 cm. The flag leaf is about 35 cm long. The lemma and palea have gold furrows on a straw background and short hairs at the upper portion. The gold color is more intense in the upper portion of the panicles, fading toward the base. Apiculus color is straw and the grains have no awns. Grain shape is intermediately slender.

Data from the National Rice Cooperative Testing Project (NRCT) of the Rice Varietal Improvement Group of the Philippine Seed Board showed that Makiling varies in plant height, from 94 to 130 cm, and matures in 114-130 d,

depending on location and environmental conditions.

It is resistant to deadhearts and moderately resistant to whiteheads caused by the striped stem borer. It is moderately susceptible to the yellow stem borer and three races of brown planthopper. It is resistant to blast, and has intermediate resistance to bacterial blight, ragged stunt, and grassy stunt virus.

Amylose content is about 20% and gel consistency is 48%. Head rice recovery is 48%; milling recovery averages 64%, with 4.5% chalky grains.

In field tests at IIRRI, Makiling showed moderate resistance to field drought and good recovery ability.

In six regional trials in the Philippines, Makiling yielded an average 2.4 t/ha over four seasons (Table 1), 4% higher than the check. In farmer-managed NRCT trials over three seasons, the yield advantage was 6% (Table 2). In regional trials, Makiling performed best in Tupi, South Cotabato, and Musuan, Bukidnon, where the soil is acid. In on-farm trials, it performed best in Calaca, Batangas, and Janiuay, Iloilo. ■

Table 1. Yield over locations^a and seasons of promising upland rice selection IR10147-113-5-1-1-5 and check UPLRi-5, National Rice Cooperative Testing Project, Philippine Seed Board, 1985-88.^b

Year, season	Yield (t/ha)						Season mean (t/ha)
	CMU	IES	LGES	MRRTC	UPLB	TSF	
	<i>UPLRi-5 (check)</i>						
1985 WS	4.0	3.4			2.5	2.4	3.1
1986 WS	1.9	2.2		2.3		3.4	2.5
1987 WS	3.0		1.2			2.8	2.3
1988 WS	3.6	2.1	1.5	1.0	2.4		"1
	<i>IR10147-113-5-1-1-5</i>						
1985	3.7	2.8			2.2	3.4	3.0
1986	3.9	1.8	-2.0	0	2.5	2.5	
1987	3.5		1.3			3.1	2.6
1988	2.3	1.1	1.5	1.2	2.1		1.6
	GMTE = 2.4	GMC = 2.5	YA = -3.9%	No.* = 3/16	No.# = 3/16		

^aCMU = Central Mindanao University, Musuan, Bukidnon, IES = Ilagan Experimental Station, Isabela, LGES = La Granja Experimental Station, Negros Occidental, MRRTC = Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Nueva Ecija, UPLB = University of the Philippines at Los Baños, College, Laguna, TSF = Tupi Seed Farm, South Cotabato. ^bGMTE = grand mean of test entry; GMC = grand mean of check YA = yield advantage of a given test entry over the check [(GMTE - GMC) + GMC] × 100, No. * = number of time a test entry has significantly higher yield than the check. No. # = lower than the check.

Table 2. Grain yield of promising upland rice selections in on-farm trials, National Rice Cooperative Testing Project, Philippine Seed Board, 1987-89 wet season.

Site	Grain yield (t/ha)					
	UPLRi-5 (Check)			IR10147-113-5-1-1-5 (PSBRi 3)		
	1987	1988	1989	1987	1988	1989
Trece Martires, Cavite		1.0	4.8		1.1	4.2
Calaca, Batangas	4.3	2.2	3.3	4.3	2.6	4.0
Padre Garcia, Batangas	4.7			4.5		
Janiuay, Iloilo #1		3.5			3.7	
Maasin, South Leyte	2.7			2.9		
Janiuay, Iloilo #2	-	3.6			4.7	
Victorias, Negros		2.2	1.7		1.9	2.1
Mean	3.9	2.5	3.2	3.9	2.8	3.4

Integrated germplasm improvement–rainfed

TP-AS42673, a high-yielding, short-duration rice for semidry and wet conditions

G. Nallathambi, J. G. Robinson, and A. S. Mathar, Agricultural Research Station (ARS), Thirupathisaram 629901, Tamil Nadu, India

In Agasteeswaram and Thovalai Taluks of Kanyakumari district, 7,000 ha of rice is direct seeded in semidry conditions during May when the summer rains start. It grows 40-50 d with available soil moisture, then is converted to wet conditions when canal water is received for irrigation. In 7,000 ha of transplanted rice, nurseries are raised Jun-Jul after receipt of canal water.

We evaluated eight improved short-duration cultures under both conditions 1989-91, with popular varieties TPS1 and TKM9 as checks. Test plots were 5 × 4 m,